

Michael Condensation of 2-Arylidene-3,4-Dihydro-1(2H) Naphthalenone with Ethyl Cyanoacetate

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Michael condensation of 2-arylidene-3,4-dihydro-1(2H) naphthalenone and ethyl cyanoacetate yields 3-cyano-4-aryl-5,6-dihydronaphtha (2,1-e) 2(1H) pyridinones in the presence of excess ammonium acetate. The same naphthapyridones were also obtained by cyclization of the intermediate Michael adducts under the influence of heat. These pyridones are converted to Mannich bases.

It has been reported¹ that ethyl cyanoacetate undergoes base-catalysed condensation with chalcones in chloroform solution using diethylamine as a base, where compounds of the type I were obtained.

Previously some pyridone derivatives were prepared by the condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with unsaturated ketones in the presence of excess of ammonium acetate.^{2,3,4,5}

In the present work the authors investigated the condensation of ethyl cyanoacetate with 2-arylidene-3,4-dihydro-1(2H) naphthalenone (IIa-e) in the presence of ammonium acetate. The condensation was carried out by heating a mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate, 2-arylidene-3,4-dihydro-1(2H) naphthalenone (II) and ammonium acetate (molar ratio 1:1:6), at 150-170° for 8 hours to give the corresponding 3-cyano-4-aryl-5,6-dihydronaphtha (2,1-e) 2(1H) pyridinones (IIIa-e).

Correct analytical values are in support for the structure assigned for the product III. Besides, the infrared spectra revealed an absorption band at 3090 cm^{-1} attributable to the-NH group⁶. Another band at 2210 cm^{-1} characteristic for-CN group⁷, and a band at 1660 cm^{-1} which is attributed to-CONH-stretching frequency⁶.

- a, Ar=C₆H₅
- b, Ar=C₆H₄.OCH₃-p
- c, Ar=C₆H₃.(OCH₃)₂-o,p
- d, Ar=C₆H₄.N(CH₃)₂-p
- e, Ar=C₆H₄.NO₂-m

It seems that the reaction involves in its first stage a Michael addition of ethyl cyanoacetate to the exocyclic double bond in the presence of ammonium acetate to give the Michael adduct (IV) which only appears as an intermediate and recycles to the corresponding naphthapyridones (III) under the influence of heat.

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In order to verify such mechanism, the Michael adducts (IVa-c), were prepared by heating a mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate and the corresponding 2-arylidene-3, 4-dihydro-1 (2H) naphthalenone in the presence of ammonium acetate at 130° for 1 hr. only.

IV

- a, Ar=C₆H₅
 b, Ar=C₆H₄.OCH₃-*p*
 c, Ar=C₆H₃.OCH₃-*o*, *p*

V

- a, Ar=C₆H₅, R=NC₅H₁₀
 b, Ar=C₆H₄.OCH₃-*p*, R=NC₅H₁₀
 c, Ar=C₆H₅, R=OH
 d, Ar=C₆H₄.OCH₃-*p*, R=OH

The products (IVa-c) were characterized by both elementary analysis, and i.r. measurements which showed stretching frequencies at 1700 cm⁻¹, 1660 cm⁻¹, 2210 cm⁻¹, and 3330 cm⁻¹ characteristic for C=O group of α-tetralone, CONH₂, C≡N, and NH group respectively.

When the above Michael adducts (IVa-c) were heated at their melting point, the above naphthapyridones (IIIa-c) were readily obtained.

The identity of naphthapyridones obtained by direct condensation of I with ethyl cyanoacetate in the presence of ammonium acetate with those obtained by cyclization of (IV) was established by analytical results, mixed melting point, and i.r. measurements.

The possible formation of N-Mannich bases (Va, b) by condensation of the amines with methylol⁸,⁹ formed as an intermediate has now been examined. The N-hydroxymethyl derivatives (Vc,d), obtained via the reaction of (IIIa), and (IIIb) with formaldehyde, condense with piperidine in the presence of methanol, giving good yields of the expected product (Va, b). These products (Va, b) were also obtained by direct interaction of piperidine, formaldehyde, and (IIIa, b) in the presence of methanol.

Experimental

Analytical data were determined in the microanalytical unit, Cairo University. Infrared spectra were recorded on SP 1000 Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected.

4-Aryl-3-cyano-5,6-dihydronaphtha(2,1-e) 2 (1H) pyridinones (IIIa-e).

A mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate (0.01 mole), 2-arylidene-3, 4-dihydro-1 (2H)-naphthalenone (IIa-e) (0.01 mole), and ammonium acetate (0.08 mole), was heated at 160-170° in an oil bath for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the yellow crystalline mass obtained was filtered, washed with water and then with ethanol. Recrystallization of the product from acetic acid gave (IIIa-e) as yellow crystals (cf. Table 1).

Formation of Michael adducts (IVa-c) :

A mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate (0.01 mole), 2-arylidene-3, 4-dihydro-1(2H)naphthalenone (IIa-c) (0.01 mole) and ammonium acetate (0.08 mole) was heated at 130° in an oil bath for one hour, and then allowed to cool. The reaction mixture was suspended in ethanol (50 ml) and the solid that separated was filtered and crystallized from acetic acid to

TABLE 1—4-ARYL-3-CYANO-5, 6-DIHYDRONAPHTHA(2,1-e) 2 (1H) PYRIDINONES (IIIa-e).

Comp.	M.P. °C	Yield	Formula	Analysis					
				Found(%)		Required(%)			
				C	H	N	C	H	N
IIIa	350	87	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	80.3	4.7	9.4	80.5	4.7	9.4
IIIb	330	85	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	76.8	5.1	8.6	76.8	4.9	8.5
IIIc above	350	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	73.4	5.2	7.8	73.7	5.0	7.8
IIId above	350	81	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	77.4	5.3	12.4	77.4	5.6	12.3
IIIe above	350	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	70.1	3.8	12.4	70.0	3.8	12.2

give the Michael adducts (IVa-c) as yellow crystalline solid. (cf. Table 2).

Cyclization of Michael adducts (IVa-c)

Compounds (IVa-c) (1.0g), were heated in an oil bath at 230-250° for 8 hours. The yellow solid was cooled, filtered and recrystallized from acetic acid to give (IIIa-c).

Action of piperidine on hydroxymethyl naphtha (2,1-e) pyridinones (Vc, and d). (Formation of N-Mannich bases (Va, and b)).

To a hot solution of the hydroxymethyl derivatives (Vc, and d) (1.0 g) in methanol (50 ml.), piperidine (1.0 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hours and cooled. The crystalline solid that separated proved to be the corresponding N-piperidinomethyl derivatives (Va,

TABLE 2—MICHAEL ADDUCTS (IV a-c)

Comp.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analysis					
				Found(%)			Required(%)		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
IVa	255	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	75.4	5.7	8.5	75.4	5.6	8.8
IVb	225	87	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	72.5	5.8	8.2	72.4	5.7	8.0
IVc	272	81	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	69.7	5.8	7.3	69.8	5.8	7.4

TABLE 3—MANNICH BASES FROM NAPHTHA (2,1-e) PYRIDINONES (IIIa, AND b)

Product	M. P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analysis					
				Found (%)			Required (%)		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
Va	above 350	87	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O	78.8	6.2	10.4	78.9	6.3	10.3
Vb	above 350	83	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂	76.4	6.3	9.6	76.2	6.3	9.8

TABLE 4—N-HYDROXYMETHYL FROM NAPHTHA (2,1-e) PYRIDINONES (IIIc, AND d)

Product	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analysis					
				Found (%)			Required (%)		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
Vc	345	83	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	77.0	5.1	8.5	76.8	4.9	8.5
Vd	350	79	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	73.6	5.3	7.7	73.7	5.0	7.8

Mannich reaction with naphtha (2,1-e) pyridinones (IIIa-b) (formation of the N-Mannich bases Va-b)

To a suspension of the naphtha(2,1-e) pyridinones (IIIa and b) (0.01 mole) and piperidine (0.02 mole) in methanol, aqueous formaldehyde (35%, 2.5 mole) was added. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 5 hours and left to stand overnight at room temperature, diluted with water and the resulting solid product was crystallized from acetic acid to give the N-Mannich bases Va, and b as yellow crystalline solid. (cf. Table 3).

Hydroxymethylation of Naphtha (2,1-e) pyridinones (IIIa, and b)

A mixture of the appropriate naphtha (2,1-e) pyridinones (IIIa & b) (1.0g), aqueous formaldehyde (35%, 10 ml) and methanol (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 hours, cooled and the separated crystalline solid was recrystallized from alcohol to give N-hydroxymethyl naphtha (2,1-e) pyridinones (Vc, and d) as yellow crystals (cf Table 4).

and b) with correct melting point and mixed melting points.

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